

1 **CRISPR/Cas9 screen for genome-wide interrogation of essential MYC-bound E-boxes in cancer cells**

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14 **ABSTRACT**

15 The transcription factor MYC is a proto-oncogene with a well-documented essential role in the
16 pathogenesis and maintenance of several types of cancer. MYC binds to specific E-box sequences in
17 the genome to regulate gene expression in a cell-type- and developmental-stage-specific manner. To
18 date, a combined analysis of essential MYC-bound E-boxes and their downstream target genes
19 important for growth of different types of cancer is missing. In this study, we designed a CRISPR/Cas9
20 library to destroy E-box sequences in a genome-wide fashion. In parallel, we used the Brunello library
21 to knock out protein-coding genes. We performed high-throughput screens with these libraries in
22 four MYC-dependent cancer cell lines – K562, ST486, HepG2 and MCF7 – which revealed several
23 essential E-boxes and genes. Among them we pinpointed crucial common and cell-type-specific MYC-
24 regulated genes involved in pathways associated with cancer development. Extensive validation of
25 our approach confirmed that E-box disruption affects MYC binding, target-gene expression and cell

26 proliferation *in vitro* as well as tumor growth *in vivo*. Our unique, well-validated tool opens new
27 possibilities to gain novel insights into MYC-dependent vulnerabilities in cancer cells.

28

29 **Key words**

30 MYC, CRISPR/Cas9, transcription factor, MYC target genes, high-throughput screen

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32 **1. ABBREVIATIONS**

33 bHLH-LZ – Basic helix-loop-helix-leucine-zipper family

34 BL – Burkitt lymphoma

35 ChIP-seq – Chromatin Immunoprecipitation followed by sequencing

36 CML – Chronic myelogenous leukemia

37 CRISPR – Clustered Regularly Interspaced Palindromic Repeats

38 (d)Cas9 – (dead)CRISPR associated protein

39 DMEM – Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium

40 FC – fold change

41 GO – Gene Ontology

42 GSEA – Gene Set Enrichment Analysis

43 MAX – MYC-associated factor X

44 PAM – Protospacer adjacent motif

45 PBS – Phosphate buffered saline

46 ROI – Regions of interest

47 RPMI – Roswell Park Memorial Institute 1640 medium

48 sgRNA – Single guide RNA

49 TF – Transcription factor

50 TSS – Transcription start site

51

52 **2. INTRODUCTION**

53 MYC is an oncogene broadly involved in many tumors. Due to amplifications, mutations,
54 translocations or posttranslational modifications, MYC is highly expressed in up to 70% of cancers [1].

55 The family of MYC transcription factors (TFs) consists of three members: C-MYC, N-MYC, and L-MYC
56 [2]. Among them, C-MYC (further called MYC) has the strongest oncogenic potential and is widely
57 deregulated in cancer, while N-MYC and L-MYC are mainly involved in neuroblastoma and lung
58 cancer, respectively [3]–[5]. MYC regulates expression of genes associated with cell cycle, apoptosis,
59 proliferation, cellular differentiation as well as strongly alters metabolism of cancer cells and
60 stimulates ribosome and mitochondrial biogenesis [6]–[9]. Altogether, this creates strong
61 dependency of cancer cells on MYC and it has been demonstrated that indeed MYC withdrawal leads
62 to tumor regression [10], [11]. Thus, targeting MYC appears as an attractive strategy for cancer
63 therapies. However, no clinically relevant MYC-targeting therapies have been developed so far [12].
64 MYC is considered an “undruggable target” due to its localization and activity in the nucleus and lack
65 of an active site for interaction with small molecules [2], [4]. Therefore, there is a need to look for
66 indirect approaches such as identification of essential MYC-regulated genes which may potentially
67 expand the repertoire of novel anti-tumor therapies.

68 MYC is a TF belonging to the basic helix-loop-helix-leucine-zipper family (bHLH-LZ) that creates
69 heterodimers with the MYC-associated factor X (MAX). The MYC/MAX complex recognizes and binds
70 to E-box motifs in DNA (canonical sequence 5'-CACGTG-3'), localized mainly in promoters and
71 enhancers. However, MYC binding is not restricted to the E-boxes. Moreover, these motifs can be
72 also recognized by other members of the bHLH-LZ family. Although MYC has been widely studied, its
73 targetome is not fully known. Thousands of genes responding to MYC activation or inhibition have
74 been identified but it is difficult to distinguish direct and indirect targets [13]–[16]. Chromatin
75 immunoprecipitation with MYC antibody followed by sequencing (MYC-ChIP-seq) indicated
76 thousands of MYC-bound sites in the genome [13], [17]–[20]. However, the set of MYC target genes
77 varies among different cell types and developmental stages [21], [22]. This may be explained by the
78 fact that MYC binds predominantly to already active promoters or enhancers and inactive genes
79 remain silent [17]. While it was shown that disruption of even one gene, crucial for MYC-dependent
80 cancer development can be sufficient to decrease cancer cell growth [23], it is still not clear which

81 MYC targets are essential for cancer cells. To date, a limited number of RNA interference screens for
82 genes essential in MYC-driven tumors have been performed. However, they either focused only on a
83 limited set of genes or were performed in normal cells with forced MYC overexpression [24]–[27].
84 This precludes their direct relevance for cancer cells. So far, thousands of MYC binding sites and
85 regulated target genes have been identified; however the question which of them are actually
86 essential for MYC-dependent cancer cells is still open.

87 In this study, we created a novel tool for the identification of essential MYC-bound E-boxes and
88 target genes in MYC-dependent cancer cells. We designed a sgRNA (single guide RNA) library for a
89 genome-wide disruption of MYC binding sites and conducted a high-throughput screen in four MYC-
90 dependent cell lines: K562 (chronic myelogenous leukemia, CML), ST486 (Burkitt lymphoma, BL),
91 HepG2 (hepatoblastoma) and MCF7 (breast cancer). Those cell lines overexpress MYC and strongly
92 depend on its high levels [28]–[31]. To allow identification of the relevant nearby genes regulated by
93 the E-boxes, we in parallel, we utilized the Brunello library for genome-wide knockout of protein-
94 coding genes. Overlapping data from both screens identified several known and novel MYC targets
95 critical for those cells. Altogether, we established a unique, well-validated tool to identify MYC-
96 regulated target genes relevant for growth of malignant cells, which opens the possibility to gain
97 novel insights into MYC-dependent vulnerabilities in cancer cells.

98

99 **3. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

100 **3.1. Cell lines**

101 The chronic myeloid leukemia cell line K562 (RRID:CVCL_0004; ordered from DSMZ, Braunschweig,
102 Germany) and Burkitt lymphoma cell line ST486 (RRID:CVCL_1712; ATCC, Manassas, VA, US) were
103 maintained in Roswell Park Memorial Institute 1640 medium (RPMI, Lonza, Basel, Switzerland)
104 supplemented with 10-20% fetal bovine serum (Sigma-Aldrich, Saint Louis, MO, US) 2mM L-
105 glutamine (Biowest, Nuaille, France), and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (Biowest) in a 5% CO₂ incubator
106 at 37°C. Hepatocellular carcinoma cell line HepG2 (RRID:CVCL_0027; DSMZ), breast cancer cell line

107 MCF7 (RRID:CVCL_0031; ECACC, Porton Down, United Kingdom) and HEK293T cell line
108 (RRID:CVCL_0063; DSMZ) used for lentiviral particles production were cultured in low glucose
109 Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM, Lonza) supplemented as described above. In addition,
110 medium for MCF7 cells was supplemented with 1x NEAA (Gibco, Waltham, MA US). Cell lines were
111 authenticated by providers in the period of three years before the experiments. They were expanded
112 and banked in our lab immediately upon receipt. After thawing, cells were cultured for experiments
113 no longer than three months. Mycoplasma tests were routinely performed and confirmed that the
114 cells were not contaminated.

115 **3.2. Plasmids**

116 The lentiCRISPR v2 (#52961) [32] and lentiCRISPR v2-dCas9 (#112233) [33] vectors were purchased
117 from Addgene (Watertown, MA, US). The plasmids contains the coding sequence of *S. pyogenes*
118 (d)Cas9 and a cloning site for the sgRNA, as well as a puromycin resistance gene allowing selection of
119 transduced cells. pGreenpuro lentivectors (SBI, Mountain View, CA, USA) with MYC shRNAs and
120 scrambled control, a kind gift of prof. Anke van den Berg [34], were used for experiments with MYC
121 knockdown.

122 **3.3. Design of the MYC-EBOX-CRISPR library**

123 To design a library of single guide RNAs (sgRNAs) for comprehensive genome-wide targeting of MYC
124 binding sites in cancer cells, we utilized publicly available MYC-ChIP-seq data from MCF7, K562 and
125 HepG2 cells [35] and Burkitt lymphoma cell lines [19]. Genomic coordinates (hg19) of MYC-ChIP
126 peaks were obtained using UCSC Table Browser and from the published data [19]. Genomic intervals
127 were concatenated, merged, and DNA sequences were retrieved using Galaxy [36]. To avoid
128 targeting coding exons, which could have resulted in disruption of the protein apart from the E-box,
129 sequences overlapping with coding exons (based on Ensembl hg19 annotation) were removed. In the
130 resulting sequences, E-box motifs were identified (canonical CACGTG, non-canonical
131 CACATG/CATGTG and CACGCG/CGCGTG) and all sgRNAs targeting these E-boxes were designed
132 based on the presence of the PAM (protospacer adjacent motif) sequence (NGG or CCN) using an in-

133 house Python script (https://github.com/tomaszwozniakihg/cas9_search_tool). The resulting sgRNAs
134 were checked for off-target binding using the CAS-OT script [37]. Only sgRNAs with at least three
135 mismatches to the potential off-targets or at least two mismatches including at least one in the seed
136 region (nt 9-20) were retained. Later analysis using the CFD algorithm, which was not available at the
137 time of library design, gave similar results. Only 81 sgRNAs included in the library had CFD scores
138 lower than 30, they are marked in red in Supplementary Table S1. The library also included 1,000
139 non-targeting sgRNAs as a negative control, and four sgRNAs against MYC as a positive control, all
140 from the Brunello library. A list of all sgRNA oligonucleotides is provided in Supplementary Table S1.
141 Supplementary File 1 contains .bed file with coordinates of targeted E-boxes which can be used in
142 UCSC Genome Browser (hg19).

143 **3.4. Cloning of the MYC-EBOX-CRISPR library and amplification of the Brunello library**

144 Oligonucleotides containing the 20 nt sgRNA sequences flanked by the sequence from the
145 lentiCRISPR_v2 vector TTTCTTGGCTTTATATATCTTGTGGAAAGGACGAAACACCG [20 nt sgRNA]
146 GTTTTAGAGCTAGAAATAGCAAGTTAAATAAGGCTAGTCCGT were synthesized by Twist Bioscience
147 (San Francisco, CA, US). 2 ng of oligonucleotide pool was amplified with the oligo-F and oligo-R
148 primers (Supplementary Table S2) using the NEBNext High-Fidelity Master Mix (New England Biolabs,
149 Ipswich, MA, US) in 20 x 25 µl PCR reactions. PCR program: 98°C 30 sec; (98°C 10 sec; 63°C 10 sec;
150 72°C 15 sec) x 7 cycles; 72°C 2 min. PCR product was purified using QIAquick PCR Purification Kit
151 (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany) and then extracted from an agarose gel with QIAquick Gel Extraction Kit
152 (Qiagen). LentiCRISPRv2_puro vector was digested with the BsmBI restriction enzyme (New England
153 Biolabs) and purified from an agarose gel. sgRNA MYC-EBOX-CRISPR library was cloned into
154 lentiCRISPRv2_puro vector using the circular polymerase extension cloning (CPEC) method as
155 described previously [38]. Briefly, 20 CPEC reactions were performed, each using 100 ng digested
156 vector, 10.8 ng amplified oligos and NEBNext High-Fidelity Master Mix. PCR program: 98°C 30 sec;
157 (98°C 10 sec; 72°C 7 min) x 5 cycles; 72°C 5 min. All PCR reactions were pooled and purified by
158 isopropanol precipitation. 300 ng of the CPEC product was used for transformation of

159 electrocompetent Endura cells (Lucigen, Middleton, WI, USA) according to the manufacturer's
160 protocol. Fourteen electroporations were performed giving in total ~7.9 million colonies and
161 resulting in ~170x coverage of the library. Bacteria were spread on 245x245 agar plates and grown
162 for 14 h at 37°C. Colonies were scraped off the plates and plasmid DNA was isolated using Plasmid
163 Plus Maxi Kit (Qiagen). The MYC-EBOX-CRISPR library was deposited in Addgene (#173195). Brunello
164 library targeting all human protein-coding genes [39] was purchased from Addgene (#73179). 50 ng
165 of the library was electroporated into Endura cells. Four electroporations were performed resulting
166 in >2,500x coverage. Quality of the MYC-EBOX-CRISPR and Brunello libraries was verified by next-
167 generation sequencing on Illumina platform (BGI, Hong-Kong).

168 **3.5. Cloning of individual sgRNA constructs**

169 For cloning of individual sgRNAs (Supplementary Table S3) into the lentiCRISPRv2_puro and
170 lentiCRISPRv2-dCas9 vectors, sense and antisense oligos containing overhangs compatible with
171 BsmBI sticky ends were synthesized by Genomed (Warsaw, Poland). Oligonucleotides were diluted in
172 annealing buffer (10mM Tris-HCl pH8, 1mM EDTA pH8, 50mM NaCl). Annealing was performed in a
173 thermocycler under conditions: 95°C 5min, 95°C (-1°C/cycle) x 70 cycles. Annealed sgRNAs were
174 ligated into the lentiCRISPRv2 and lentiCRISPRv2-dCas9 vectors digested with BsmBI restriction
175 enzyme at 1:5 vector:insert molar ratio with T4 DNA ligase (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA, US). 1 µl of
176 ligation reaction was transformed into JM109 competent cells (Promega, Madison, WI, USA). Plasmid
177 DNA from single colonies was isolated using Plasmid Plus Maxi Kit (Qiagen). Sequences of individual
178 sgRNA constructs were confirmed by Sanger sequencing (Genomed).

179 **3.6. Generation of lentiviral particles**

180 For large scale production of lentiviral particles ~7.5 million HEK293T cells were plated in a T75 flask
181 one day prior to transfection. Next day, ~80% confluent cells were transfected with packaging
182 plasmids psPAX (11.2 µg) and pMD2.G (7.5 µg), and MYC-EBOX-CRISPR or Brunello library plasmid (15
183 µg) using lipofectamine 2000 reagent (Invitrogen). One day after transfection medium was replaced
184 with 7.5 ml DMEM supplemented with 10% FBS. Two and three days post-transfection Brunello and

185 MYC-EBOX-CRISPR lentiviral supernatants were filtered through 0.45 μm filter and stored at -80°C .
186 For small scale production of lentiviral particles 1 million HEK293T cells were plated per well on a 6-
187 well plate and transfected the next day with packaging plasmids psPAX (1.5 μg) and pMD2.G (1 μg),
188 and lentiCRISPRv2 plasmid (2 μg) using calcium phosphate transfection method (Invitrogen). One day
189 after transfection medium was replaced with 1.1 ml DMEM supplemented with 10% FBS and
190 lentiviral supernatant was collected as described above.

191 **3.7. Determination of virus titer and cell transduction for screening**

192 1.8-2.7 million cells were plated per well in a 12-well plate and transduced with different amounts of
193 virus. 4 mg/ml polybrene was added and cells were spun down in plates (33°C , 1000x g, 2h). After
194 spinfection, additional 1 ml of medium was added. 24 h after transduction cells were washed and
195 plated out in four wells for each condition, two wells with 0.3-3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ puromycin and two wells
196 without puromycin. Medium with puromycin was changed after three days. After four days of
197 selection, cells were counted and the percentage of surviving cells relative to cells not treated with
198 puromycin was calculated. From this we determined the amount of virus resulting in $\sim 30\%$ surviving
199 cells, which implies that approximately 85% of transduced cells were infected by a single virus.

200 ~ 78 million cells for the MYC-EBOX-CRISPR library and ~ 130 million cells for the Brunello library were
201 transduced in duplicate with the amount of virus that results in $\sim 30\%$ transduced cells, in the same
202 conditions as described above. After four days of selection with puromycin (T0) part of the cells was
203 collected for DNA isolation. Remaining cells were further cultured for 20 population doublings. At
204 each passage, the amount of cells corresponding to a 500x coverage (24 million for MYC-EBOX-
205 CRISPR, 38 million for Brunello library) were cultured in RPMI medium with 0.1-1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ puromycin
206 and collected at the final timepoint (T1).

207 **3.8. Preparation of libraries for next-generation sequencing of the plasmid pool or genomic**

208 **DNA**

209 sgRNA sequences from the MYC-EBOX-CRISPR and Brunello library plasmids were amplified in PCR
210 reaction using High Fidelity MasterMix 2x (New England Biolabs) and primers containing Illumina

211 adaptors, an 8 nt barcode specific for each library (reverse primer) and a variable length (9-18 nt)
212 stagger sequence to increase library complexity (forward primer) [40] (Supplementary Table S2). PCR
213 products were pooled and purified using QIAquick PCR Purification Kit (Qiagen). Amplicons were
214 analyzed on agarose gel and then extracted using QIAquick Gel Extraction Kit (Qiagen). Quality check
215 and quantification of libraries were performed by qPCR using KAPA Library Quantification Kit (Roche,
216 Basel, Switzerland).

217 Genomic DNA collected from cells infected with MYC-EBOX-CRISPR and Brunello libraries was
218 isolated using GENTRA Puregene Kit (Qiagen). PCR was performed to amplify the sgRNA sequences
219 integrated in genomic DNA. DNA from 23 million cells (MYC-EBOX-CRISPR) and 38 million cells
220 (Brunello) was amplified in 80-120 (MYC-EBOX-CRISPR) and 130-210 (Brunello) individual 50 μ l PCR
221 reactions per sample with 3-3.5 μ g DNA input as described above. PCR products were purified,
222 analyzed on agarose gel, pooled based on band intensities, and extracted from gel as described
223 above. Determination of quality and quantification of libraries was performed by qPCR (Kapa Library
224 Quantification Kit).

225 **3.9. NGS and data analysis**

226 NGS was performed on Illumina X-Ten platform at BGI (Hong-Kong). Reads were trimmed to remove
227 adaptor sequences and split based on barcodes for individual samples. Number of reads obtained for
228 each sample is given in Supplementary Table S4. For sgRNA enumeration, raw reads were processed
229 with a Python script [40]. Only sgRNAs with no mismatches were counted. Fold change and p values
230 for each gene and E-box were calculated with DeSeq2. Read counts for all sgRNAs for a given E-box
231 or gene were summed up and DeSeq2 analysis was performed, which includes the estimation of size-
232 factors, the variance stabilization using a parametric fit and a Wald-Test for difference in log₂ fold
233 changes between the untreated and treated data [41]. Adjusted p-value 0.001 was used as a cut-off
234 for identification of significantly depleted or enriched E-boxes (MYC-EBOX-CRISPR library) and genes
235 (Brunello library).

236 **3.10. Determination of CRISPR/Cas9 editing efficiency by TIDE**

237 To confirm CRISPR/Cas9 disruption of selected E-boxes, DNA was isolated from K562 cells at day 7
238 after transduction with individual sgRNAs targeting the selected E-boxes. Genomic regions of ~500-
239 800 bp flanking E-box sequences were amplified by PCR (primer sequences in Supplementary Table
240 S2). Amplicons were sequenced using the Sanger method (Genomed) and analyzed with TIDE
241 calculator (<https://tide-calculator.nki.nl>) [42], using indel size range of 50.

242 **3.11. RNA isolation and qRT-PCR**

243 Total RNA was isolated from K562 cells using Quick-RNA™ Miniprep Kit (Zymo Research, Irvine, CA,
244 US). cDNA was synthesized from 500 ng RNA using QuantiTect® Reverse Transcription Kit (Qiagen).
245 qPCR on 5 ng cDNA was performed on CFX96 Touch qPCR System (BioRad, Hercules, CA, US) using
246 PowerUp SYBR Green Master Mix (Applied Biosystems, Waltham, MA US). Expression was
247 normalized to TBP. All experiments were conducted in two independent biological replicates, each
248 with three technical replicates.

249 **3.12. Growth assay**

250 Growth assay was performed using CellTiter-Glo® Luminescent Cell Viability Assay (Promega). 1×10^3
251 K562 cells infected with sgRNA lentiviral constructs were plated in triplicate on 96-well plates. 100 μ l
252 Cell-Titer Glo reagent diluted 1:2 in PBS was added per well after 1h (baseline level), 48h and 96h.
253 The luminescent signal was measured using a GloMax microplate reader (Promega). Experiments
254 were performed in three independent biological replicates. Growth rate was calculated at 48h and
255 96h relative to the 1h measurement.

256 **3.13. Chromatin immunoprecipitation assay**

257 10 M of K562 cells infected with sgRNAs targeting selected E-box sequences were fixed to crosslink
258 DNA with chromatin-associated proteins according to the Active Motif protocol. Briefly, cells were
259 fixed for 20 min by adding 1/10 volume of 37% formaldehyde solution and then neutralized by
260 adding 1/20 volume of 2.5 M glycine. Next, K562 cells were washed using PBS-Igepal, snap-frozen on
261 dry ice and stored at -80°C. Chromatin immunoprecipitation with anti-MYC antibody (sc-764, Santa
262 Cruz, Dallas, TX, US) followed by qPCR was performed by Active Motif (La Hulpe, Belgium).

263 **3.14. Luciferase reporter assay**

264 To confirm that sequences containing selected E-boxes drive transcription in a MYC-dependent way,
265 we conducted luciferase reporter assay. MYC binding sites as defined by peaks from MYC-ChIP-seq
266 data were amplified by PCR from DNA of K562 cells. For chr11_BS79 the amplified sequence was
267 shorter to omit two other non-essential E-boxes present in the peak. Primers contained sequences to
268 create overhangs for XhoI and SacI restriction sites (Supplementary Table S2) for cloning into the
269 pGL4.23 vector, upstream of the firefly luciferase gene under minimal promoter (#E8411, Promega).
270 K562 cells were transduced with MYC shRNAs or scrambled control. After selection with puromycin
271 for 4 days, 1×10^5 cells were co-transfected using Lipofectamine LTX with 500 ng pGL4.23 vector with
272 E-box constructs and 5 ng pRL-SV40 vector containing Renilla luciferase (#E2231, Promega). 24h after
273 transfection cells were lysed and luminescence was measured using Dual Luciferase Reporter Assay
274 on GloMax (Promega). Firefly luminescence was normalized to Renilla. The experiments were
275 performed in three independent biological replicates, each with triplicate transfection.

276 **3.15. Gene Ontology, Gene Set Enrichment Analysis and TCGA data**

277 For each E-box, the nearest genes with transcription start site (TSS) within 50 kb both upstream and
278 downstream were retrieved using Galaxy. Gene ontology analysis was conducted using DAVID
279 Functional Annotation Tool v6.8b [43], [44] on 1) genes marked as essential in the Brunello screen
280 and 2) a subset of at least two-fold depleted genes within 50 kb of essential E-boxes from MYC-EBOX-
281 CRISPR screen. Pre-ranked gene set enrichment analysis (GSEA) [45], [46] was performed on log₂ fold
282 change values of all genes in the Brunello library. To complement this analysis and reveal processes
283 in which genes regulated by essential E-boxes are involved, we have taken a subset of genes from the
284 Brunello screen which were near at least two-fold depleted E-boxes. Hallmark (H) and curated (C2)
285 gene sets v7.4 were used for analysis. In addition, we analyzed expression of selected genes in tumor
286 and normal tissues using data from the UALCAN portal and explored potential relationship with
287 survival [47], [48].

288

289 **3.16. Tumor xenografts**

290 The experiments were carried out in 2 months old NOD-SCID mice (NOD, CB17-Prkdcscid/NCrCrI)
291 bred and housed in Animal Facility in IHG PAS, Poznan, Poland. Animals were provided sterilized food
292 and water ad libitum and were maintained on a regular 12-h day/night cycle at no more than five
293 adult animals per individually ventured cage. The Local Ethical Committee for Animal Research at
294 Poznan University of Life Sciences approved the protocol for the experiments performed in the mice
295 (LECfAR decision 58/2020). All animal experiments were performed under relevant guidelines and
296 regulations according to 3R rules. The experimental groups were designed to include the same ratio
297 of male/female individuals. HepG2 cells stably expressing firefly luciferase were transduced with
298 control non-targeting sgRNA or sgRNAs targeting E-boxes: chr1_BS1363_CACAATG,
299 chr11_BS79_CGCGTG and chr18_BS691_CATGTG. 1×10^6 cells per dose/ 2×10^6 per mouse cells were
300 resuspended in the mixture of medium and Matrigel (Merck) and injected subcutaneously into the
301 right and left flank of each mouse. Mice were randomly classified into 4 groups (n = 4-8 tumors per
302 group). In vivo bioluminescence imaging was performed every 7 days for 5 weeks. Mice were
303 anesthetized with 5% isoflurane and maintained with 2% isoflurane during imaging procedures.
304 Luciferase-based bioluminescence imaging was performed with an IVIS Lumina LT imaging system
305 (Perkin Elmer) equipped with a camera box and warming stage. Following intraperitoneal injection of
306 150 μ l of IVISbrite D-Luciferin Potassium Salt Bioluminescent Substrate (XenoLight) (Perkin Elmer)
307 dissolved in phosphate buffered saline (PBS), mice were immediately imaged with sequential 5
308 numbers of segments in every 2 min delay with 2 seconds exposures. Images were captured and
309 bioluminescence intensity was quantitated using Living Image 3.2 acquisition and analysis software
310 (Caliper Life Sciences, Hopkinton, MA). Total flux values were determined by drawing regions of
311 interest (ROI) of identical size over each mouse and are presented in photons (p)/second (sec). All
312 animals were sacrificed after 5 weeks of inoculation. Tumor volume was determined by a vernier
313 caliper and calculated by the formula: volume = (width² × length)/2.

314

315 **4. RESULTS**

316 **4.1. Generation of the MYC-EBOX-CRISPR library for a genome-wide disruption of MYC binding**
317 **sites**

318 We confirmed that cell lines selected for this study: K562, ST486, HepG2 and MCF7 express high
319 levels of MYC and depend on MYC for their growth (Supplementary Figure S1). From publicly
320 available MYC-ChIP-seq data in MYC-dependent K562, MCF7, HepG2 [35], and BL cell lines [19] we
321 obtained 58,503 MYC binding sites, which contained 43,153 E-box motifs. 2,208 of them were
322 located in the coding exons and were excluded to prevent effects due to disruption of the protein.
323 Based on the presence of PAM sequence, we designed 56,688 unique sgRNAs targeting the
324 remaining 26,653 E-boxes (65.1%). After excluding sgRNAs with predicted off-target binding, we
325 finally obtained 45,350 sgRNAs targeting 24,981 E-boxes (61%) (Figure 1A, Supplementary Table S1).
326 Half of the E-boxes were targeted by more than one sgRNA (Figure 1B). The majority of E-boxes were
327 located in introns (58.4%) or intergenic regions (33.2%) (Figure 1C). 61% of the E-boxes targeted by
328 our MYC-EBOX-CRISPR library were bound by MYC only in one cell line, while 6% of the E-boxes were
329 commonly bound by MYC in all four cell lines (Figure 1D). This is in line with the high cell-type
330 specificity of MYC targets. Although the MYC-EBOX-CRISPR library was designed based on the data
331 from selected four cell lines, analysis of available MYC-ChIP-seq data from 11 cell lines revealed that
332 16-60% MYC binding sites were targeted by the library sgRNAs (Figure 1E). This indicates that the
333 MYC-EBOX-CRISPR library can be widely applied for studies in various cell lines.

334 Next generation sequencing revealed high quality of the cloned MYC-EBOX-CRISPR library. All sgRNAs
335 were present and the skew ratio of 90th to 10th percentile was only 1.76, indicating a uniform
336 representation of all constructs in the library (Figure 1F). The quality of the amplified Brunello library
337 also conformed to the recommended requirements (Supplementary Figure S2). Thus, we generated a
338 high quality MYC-EBOX-CRISPR library for genome-wide targeting of MYC-bound E-boxes that can be
339 universally used in various cell lines.

4.2. High-throughput screen for functional MYC binding sites and target genes essential for growth of cancer cells

To identify essential MYC binding sites and target genes, we conducted a genome-wide high-throughput CRISPR/Cas9 screen with the MYC-EBOX-CRISPR library (46,354 sgRNA) targeting E-boxes and the Brunello library (77,441 sgRNA) [39] targeting protein-coding genes (Figure 2A). Four cancer cell lines were infected in duplicate aiming at ~500x coverage of each sgRNA in both libraries and a 30% transduction efficiency. The obtained values are shown in Table 1. Cells were collected at T0 (after puromycin selection) and T1 (after 20 population doublings) and the abundance of sgRNA constructs was determined by NGS (Figure 2B, Supplementary Table S5, S6). Almost none of the non-targeting sgRNAs was depleted ≥ 2 -fold in both replicates and 2-4 sgRNAs targeting MYC showed consistently decreased abundance at T1. 9,112-11,970 sgRNAs from the Brunello library and 517-3,034 sgRNAs from the MYC-EBOX-CRISPR library were consistently ≥ 2 -fold depleted in both replicates (Supplementary Figure S3). Considering the combined effect of all sgRNAs targeting a given gene or E-box, using DESeq2 algorithm, 354-1,992 genes (Supplementary Table S7) and 56-97 E-boxes (Supplementary Table S8) were identified as essential for growth of selected cancer cells ($p_{adj} < 0.001$), while 3-9 E-boxes and 5-18 genes were significantly enriched (Figure 2C, 2D). Initial analysis in K562 cell line revealed 152 essential E-boxes. 40% of them were localized on chromosome 22, near the breakpoint in *BCR* involved in the t(9;22) translocation (Figure 2E). Hits observed in this region are most likely not caused by targeting essential genes but due to massive CRISPR/Cas9-mediated DNA cleavage within this tandemly amplified region in K562 cells, as observed previously [49]. Indeed, an orthogonal approach with dCas9 which does not induce DNA cleavage but blocks E-box sites to prevent MYC binding demonstrated no effect on K562 cell growth for two sgRNAs from chromosome 22q11 (Supplementary Figure S4A). Therefore E-boxes from the amplified region on 22q11 and 9q34 were excluded from further analysis.

364 Analysis of essential E-boxes revealed that 20-32% were localized close to genes essential for cancer
365 cells, as identified in our screens with the Brunello library. Moreover, 42-49% of adjacent genes are
366 well known MYC-regulated targets (Supplementary Table S8).

367 Thus, our CRISPR/Cas9 screen revealed known and novel MYC-dependent vulnerabilities in the
368 studied cancer cells.

369 **4.3. Common and cell type-specific MYC-regulated processes**

370 To determine main functions of essential and MYC-regulated genes identified in our high-throughput
371 screens we conducted Gene Ontology (GO) and Gene Set Enrichment (GSEA) analyses. Genes
372 essential in the Brunello screen were involved in several GO processes common for all cell lines, such
373 as: metabolism, ribosome biogenesis, metabolism of nucleic acids, splicing and translation (Figure
374 3A). GSEA results revealed very similar processes, majority of which were shared between cell lines.
375 In addition, some cell-specific processes emerged, such as DNA repair in K562, aminoacyl tRNA
376 biosynthesis in ST486, oxidative phosphorylation in HepG2 and cell cycle in MCF7 (Supplementary
377 Table S9). On the other hand, genes localized near depleted E-boxes showed a more diverse
378 spectrum of processes, reflecting the limited overlap from the screen and indicating involvement of
379 cell line-specific processes regulated by MYC. We identified GO processes such as metabolism and
380 ribosome biogenesis but also histone modifications, protein localization, RNA processing and
381 metabolism (Figure 3B). GSEA for genes nearby E-boxes highlighted translation, ribosome biogenesis,
382 RNA processing and tumor invasiveness as processes common for all cell lines. Cell type-specific
383 processes were much more prevalent and diverse, with no particular predominant terms emerging
384 for each cell line (Supplementary Table S10). Interestingly,
385 REACTOME_REGULATION_OF_EXPRESSION_OF_SLITS_AND_ROBOS was a recurrently enriched gene
386 set in all cell lines, in Brunello as well as MYC-EBOX-CRISPR results. SLIT/ROBO pathway is involved in
387 axon guidance and cell migration but it has been also implicated in tumor growth, migration,
388 angiogenesis, and microenvironment [50].

389 Overlap of essential E-boxes for four cancer cell lines revealed only three (1%) common E-boxes
390 (Figure 3C): chr1_BS1363_CACAATG with neighbor genes *MECR* and *PTPRU*, chr11_BS79_CGCGTG
391 localized near *RPLP2* and *PIDD1*, and chr18_BS691_CATGTG adjacent to *RBFA* and *TXNL4A*. 10 E-
392 boxes (3%) overlapped in 3 out of 4 cell lines, while majority of E-boxes (59-87%) were essential only
393 in one cell line. Detailed snapshots of exemplary common and specific E-box loci are provided in
394 Supplementary Figures S5 and S6. Crucial genes identified in the Brunello screen showed greater
395 overlap, with 135 (5%) genes common for all cell lines and 788 (29%) in 3 out of 4, and only 10-30%
396 cell type-specific genes (Figure 3D).

397 Due to low number of genes depleted in the Brunello screen and located near essential E-boxes
398 specific for each cell line, GO and GSEA analyses did not reveal any significant terms. However, we
399 noticed some interesting processes, such as transcription, RNA processing, MAPK cascade, DNA
400 repair, replication, translation and protein transport or ubiquitination (Supplementary Table S11). To
401 further explore the potential relevance of those genes, we analyzed their expression in liver and
402 breast cancer and determined their potential association with survival using The Cancer Genome
403 Atlas (TCGA) data. 14 out of 18 depleted ($\log_2FC < -1$) genes near essential E-boxes in HepG2 cells
404 were significantly and >1.5-fold overexpressed in liver tumors compared to normal tissue. Moreover,
405 high expression of 12 out of 18 genes was associated with significantly worse survival
406 (Supplementary Table S11). This highlights the relevance of E-boxes and genes identified in our
407 screen in patient samples. However, in breast cancer samples only 4 out of 17 genes were
408 significantly and >1.5-fold overexpressed, and only one gene – *ZMYND8* – was associated with
409 patient survival.

410 **4.4. Validation of the approach**

411 To validate the results of the screen and confirm robustness of our approach for identification of
412 MYC-dependent vulnerabilities in cancer cells, we focused on the top 10 most significantly depleted
413 E-boxes in K562 cells. Of these, we included for validation six that were located nearby a protein-
414 coding gene that was at least 4-fold depleted in Brunello screen (chr3_BS897_CATGTG,

415 chr11_BS79_CGCGTG, chr11_BS2113_CACATG, chr13_BS121_CGCGTG, chr17_BS377_CACGTG,
416 chr19_BS2255_CACATG), and two E-boxes adjacent to long non-coding RNA (lncRNA) genes
417 (chr10_BS212_CACATG, chr2_BS1664_CACGTG). The remaining two of top 10 E-boxes were in
418 vicinity of non-essential genes and were not considered for validation. In addition, we also included
419 for validation a non-essential E-box, chr17_BS377_CGCGTG which was located 12 nt downstream of
420 chr17_BS377_CACGTG (Supplementary Figure S7), to gain further insight into MYC regulation at this
421 locus.

422 Cells were transduced with individual sgRNAs targeting selected E-boxes. First, we checked whether
423 our approach allows for efficient disruption of E-box motifs. TIDE analysis confirmed DNA editing
424 with >90% efficiency for all sgRNAs. The spectrum of mutations varied between individual constructs,
425 with small 1-2 nt indels being most prevalent (Figure 4A, Supplementary Figure S8A).

426 Next, we confirmed that for 6 out of 8 selected E-boxes expression of adjacent genes was
427 significantly affected (Figure 4B, Supplementary Figure S8B). In some instances, expression of both
428 genes nearby an E-box was altered, while in others one of the genes was not affected at all or to a
429 lesser extent. Interestingly, for chr17_BS377 we observed strong downregulation of *PFAS* when
430 targeting the essential CACGTG E-box (sg1), but much weaker effect for the non-essential CGCGTG E-
431 box (sgB1 and sgB2). For E-box chr2_BS1664 we could not reliably detect expression of the adjacent
432 lncRNAs, neither in control nor CRISPR/Cas9 edited samples. For chr11_BS2113 the closest gene was
433 *PRKRIR* located >50 kb, and we did not observe an impact on its expression. Thus, disruption of E-
434 boxes with CRISPR/Cas9 modulates expression of target genes and can indicate genes regulated by
435 MYC within a given locus.

436 We further validated the effect on cell growth observed in high-throughput screens for three E-boxes
437 with the strongest effect on expression of adjacent genes: chr10_BS212, chr11_BS79 and
438 chr17_BS377. We conducted growth assays in K562 cells transduced with sgRNAs for E-box
439 disruption and knockout of adjacent genes, and shRNAs for knockdown of the lncRNA *PRKCQ-AS1*,
440 which was not included in the Brunello screen. For all sgRNAs targeting chosen E-boxes we observed

441 a significant decrease in cell growth, consistent with the results of the screen. We confirmed that
442 within chr17_BS377, only the CACGTG E-box targeted by sg1 is essential for K562 cells growth.
443 Moreover, knockout/knockdown of genes adjacent to each E-box also significantly reduced cell
444 growth, in line with the effect observed in the Brunello screen (Figure 4C). Although both adjacent
445 genes showed decreased expression after disruption of chr10_BS212 and chr11_BS79, only one of
446 each pair was essential for cell growth. Combining the outcome of E-box disruption on expression of
447 adjacent genes with the effect of individual genes' knockout on cell growth allowed us to pinpoint
448 the MYC targets relevant for the cell growth.

449 To confirm direct MYC binding and regulation of transcription, we performed a luciferase reporter
450 assay for the three selected E-boxes. We observed decreased luminescent signal for all three MYC
451 binding sites upon MYC knockdown (Figure 4D). This indicates that binding of MYC to these
452 sequences results in MYC-dependent transcription. Moreover, MYC-ChIP in cells transduced with
453 sgRNAs targeting two of the selected E-boxes confirmed decreased MYC binding to chr17_BS377 and
454 chr10_BS212 as compared to non-targeting control sgRNA. Disruption of chr11_BS79 did not affect
455 the strength of MYC binding (Figure 4E).

456 As an alternative approach, to further validate the importance of MYC binding we utilized dCas9 to
457 block the E-box sequences rather than to disrupt them when using WT Cas9. RT-qPCR in cells
458 transduced with dCas9 and sgRNAs targeting chr10_BS212, chr11_BS79 and chr17_BS377 showed
459 the same pattern of gene expression as for WT Cas9 (Supplementary Figure S4A). In addition, the
460 effect on cell growth for chr11_BS79 and chr17_BS377 was similar with dCas9 and WT Cas9
461 (Supplementary Figure S4B), while we did not notice change in K562 growth for the sgRNA targeting
462 chr10_BS212. These results further confirm that disturbing MYC binding at these positions is
463 causative for the observed effects on expression of target genes and cell growth.

464 Three E-boxes included in the validation in K562 cells were also essential in ST486 cells:
465 chr3_BS897_CATGTG, chr10_BS212_CACATG, and chr11_BS79_CGCGTG. We confirmed decreased

466 cell growth and deregulated expression of nearby genes upon targeting of those E-boxes in ST486
467 cells (Supplementary Figure S9).

468 Altogether, we confirmed that our approach allows for efficient disruption of E-box motifs, which
469 results in decreased MYC binding and affects expression of target genes.

470 **4.5. E-box disruption inhibits tumor growth *in vivo* in a mouse xenograft model**

471 To validate the growth inhibitory effect *in vivo*, we established bioluminescent xenografts of HepG2
472 cells transduced with sgRNAs targeting the three common E-boxes essential in all cell lines:
473 chr1_BS1363_CACAATG, chr11_BS79_CGCGTG and chr18_BS691_CATGTG, and the non-targeting
474 control. We chose HepG2 cells based on the feasibility of establishing the xenograft model. First, we
475 confirmed the negative effect of targeting those E-boxes on cell growth *in vitro* (Figure 5A). The
476 dynamics of tumor growth was monitored once a week over five weeks via *in vivo* bioluminescence
477 imaging. We observed a delayed tumor growth for xenografts of chr11_BS79_and chr18_BS691
478 compared to the control, while chr1_BS1363 xenografts grew even faster than the control (Figure 5B
479 and C, Supplementary Figure S10). Tumor volumes of chr1_BS1363 and chr11_BS79_CGCGTG
480 xenografts were significantly smaller as compared to control tumors (in case of chr11 one tumor did
481 not grow at all). Xenografts of chr1_BS1363 were on average bigger than control tumors, although
482 we observed considerable variability between individual tumors (Figure 5D and E). These results
483 confirm that targeting E-boxes can decrease tumor growth *in vivo*. At the same time, they highlight
484 the importance of *in vivo* validation, as additional factors may play a role and result in a different
485 outcome than *in vitro*, as shown here in case of chr1_BS1363.

486 **4.6. Implications of the sequence context on E-box functionality**

487 We observed that in some cases with a +1 insertion, the inserted nucleotide did not change the E-box
488 motif (i.e. G added before the last G in the E-box or C inserted after the first C in the E-box). For some
489 sgRNAs the estimated frequency of such DNA edits reached up to ~50% (Supplementary Table S12).
490 Despite apparently not affecting the E-box sequence, we did observe an effect on cell growth and
491 expression of adjacent genes on bulk infected K562 cells. To gain further insights into the E-box

492 grammar, we focused on the E-box CACATG on chromosome 10 (chr10_BS212) with a cut site directly
493 before the last G in the E-box (CACAT*G) and the highest percentage (56%) of +1 insertions with an
494 additional G (CACGTGG).

495 We successfully established 24 clones of K562 cells with varied mutations and/or WT sequence on all
496 3 alleles (K562 cells are triploid) (Supplementary Table S13). No significant differences between WT
497 homozygotes and mutants were observed in the expression levels of the nearby PRKCQ gene that
498 was not essential for K562 cells in the Brunello screen. In contrast, expression of the adjacent lncRNA
499 PRKCQ-AS1, whose downregulation negatively affected K562 cell growth, was significantly decreased
500 in +G homozygotes, to a similar extent as in clones with other indels which clearly disrupted the E-
501 box (Figure 6A). This indicated that even though the E-box motif sequence *per se* was not changed,
502 its functionality was affected.

503 This prompted us to look at the sequences flanking the E-boxes. Analysis of the nucleotide frequency
504 20 nt upstream and downstream of non-essential E-boxes showed uniform distribution of
505 nucleotides. In contrast, there were marked differences at particular positions flanking essential E-
506 boxes (Figure 6B). Statistical analysis of 10 nt upstream/downstream revealed that certain
507 nucleotides were significantly over- or underrepresented in the neighborhood of essential E-boxes
508 (Figure 6C). Since E-boxes are (quasi)palindromic and can be read on either strand, G at +1 equals C
509 at -1 etc. The strongest bias in nucleotide composition was observed at positions +/-1 nt, and 3-7 nt.
510 In particular, we observed that G immediately after or C immediately before essential E-boxes was
511 disfavored. Thus, we speculate that the immediate context of E-boxes might affect their functionality.
512 This could explain why such changes without apparent disruption of the E-box affected expression of
513 adjacent genes and cell viability.

514

515 **5. DISCUSSION**

516 Despite decades of research, MYC still evades full comprehension and therapeutic targeting. To
517 understand the mechanisms underlying cancer cell dependency on MYC, it is essential to determine

518 the crucial genes regulated by this TF. Therefore, the aim of this study was to identify on a genome-
519 wide scale functional MYC binding sites and corresponding target genes essential for cancer cells
520 growth. To this end, we have established a novel CRISPR/Cas9-based tool to disrupt MYC-bound E-
521 boxes.

522 Extensive validation of our approach confirmed efficient E-box disruption, decreased
523 expression of adjacent genes and reduced MYC binding upon CRISPR/Cas9 editing of selected E-
524 boxes. No change in MYC binding for the E-box on chr11 can be potentially explained by the presence
525 of another, non-essential E-box, chr11_BS79_CACGCG ~100 bp downstream of the analyzed E-box
526 chr11_BS79_CGCGTG (Supplementary Figure S7B). Resolution of CHIP-PCR with DNA fragments of ca.
527 500 bp does not allow to distinguish such close binding sites. Finally, using individual sgRNAs we
528 confirmed that E-box disruption or knockout of adjacent genes significantly decreased K562 cell
529 proliferation, in line with the results of the screens. However, we observed some discrepancies using
530 a parallel dCas9 approach. We validated the effect on cell growth for two out of three E-boxes but for
531 chr10_BS212 we did not observe decreased proliferation with dCas9, despite a similar effect on
532 expression of two adjacent genes *PRKCQ* and *PRKCQ-AS1*. Similar inconsistencies have also been
533 reported for targeting p53 binding sites with WT Cas9 and dCas9 with an overall limited overlap [51]
534 and this phenomenon requires further investigation.

535 Notably, using our strategy it was possible to determine which E-boxes are essential for cell viability
536 and identify relevant regulated target genes. This is important since we demonstrated that not all E-
537 boxes in a binding site affected cell growth and target gene expression. Similarly, not all genes
538 adjacent to an E-box responded to E-box disruption and were crucial for cancer cells. In our screen,
539 68-80% of essential E-boxes were not localized near essential genes, but this might be an
540 underestimation as we checked only the first TSS within 50 kb up- and downstream of each E-box.
541 Moreover, due to chromatin organization, the relevant target may be much further away. In
542 addition, MYC also regulates non-coding RNAs, which were not included in this general analysis, yet
543 might be essential. Combination of the MYC-EBOX-CRISPR screen with single cell RNA sequencing

544 would add another layer of information to this experimental setup and allow direct identification of
545 genes responding to E-box disruption.

546 Essential genes identified in the Brunello screen showed a substantial overlap, and 77% of them
547 belong to the panel of pan-essential genes [52]. The number of essential genes identified in MCF7
548 was lower than in other cell lines (354 vs 1,226-1,992). This may be due to less efficient gene
549 knockout as these cells are hypertriploid to hypotetraploid. Previous genome-wide screens in MCF7
550 cells also revealed a highly variable number of essential genes (527-2,463) [53]. GO and GSEA
551 analyses revealed processes common for all studied cell lines which indicates that different types of
552 cancers rely on the same factors for their growth [54]. On the other hand, the overlap between
553 essential E-boxes was very limited and analysis of adjacent genes revealed a bigger spectrum of cell
554 type-specific processes. This observation is in line with the fact that MYC acts within the pre-defined
555 transcriptional landscape which varies between cell types and developmental stages, and regulates
556 expression of specific target genes [17], [21], [55], [56].

557 A recent study identified 1344 MYC-dependent genes ($\log_2FC < -0.58$, $p < 0.05$) in K562 cells using
558 SLAM-seq upon MYC disruption [57]. 1035 of these genes had an E-box within 50 kb that was
559 included in the MYC-EBOX-CRISPR library. Of these, 284 genes were localized near an E-box that was
560 at least 1.5-fold depleted in our screen in K562 cells (Supplementary Figure S11). This limited overlap
561 may be due to the fact that in our study we focused on MYC targets which were essential for K562
562 cells growth, while SLAM-seq included all targets. On the other hand, due to sgRNA design in our
563 screen we might have missed some E-boxes relevant for target genes. This highlights the need for
564 integration of multiple approaches for identification of essential MYC targets.

565 Interestingly, our study provided also some novel insights into the grammar of E-boxes and their
566 surrounding sequences. We observed significantly different frequencies of specific nucleotides at
567 certain positions in essential vs non-essential E-boxes. This observation provides novel indications
568 about E-box functionality and demonstrates the usefulness of high-throughput CRISPR/Cas9
569 mutagenesis for studying TF binding sites. Previous studies showed that DNA flexibility and structure

570 determined by the flanking sequences impacts binding of TFs [58], including closely related TFs from
571 the bHLH family: MYC, MAX and MAD [59], [60]. Phylogenetic comparisons revealed strong sequence
572 conservation of E-boxes and also their flanking regions among species [61]. Moreover, it was recently
573 reported that MYC is first engaged in open chromatin regions *via* non-specific binding, while
574 recognition of specific sequences stabilizes binding of MYC to DNA and promotes its transcriptional
575 activity [62].

576 A limitation of our study is that we were not able to target all E-boxes within the MYC-bound loci.
577 Our library was designed for the canonical E-box motif (CACGTG) and two most common non-
578 canonical ones (CATGTG and CACGCG) [18], [20], [63], [64]. 29,811 (51%) of the 58,503 MYC peaks
579 from CHIP data contained at least one of those E-boxes. Other, less common E-box motifs not
580 included in our design (CACGAG, CACGAT, CATGCG, CACGTT, CACGCT) together contributed only to
581 6,348 sites (11%), while the remaining MYC peaks did not contain any of the above mentioned E-
582 boxes. It has been observed that MYC can also bind to regions without any known E-box sequence
583 [20], [63] but those binding sites cannot be targeted with our approach. For the 43,153 E-boxes
584 identified within the 29,811 MYC peaks, we were able to design sgRNAs targeting 24,981 E-boxes.
585 This was due to either lack of PAM sequence nearby (35% of E-boxes not included in our library) or
586 strong off-target activity of designed sgRNAs (only 4% of E-boxes not targeted). This could be
587 overcome with a complementary approach using variant Cas9 nucleases with different PAM
588 requirements.

589 A potential flaw in our approach could be the fact that other bHLH proteins can bind to E-boxes and
590 affect transcription [65]. Therefore, effect of E-box disruption might be also related to other
591 interactors. However, several findings strongly suggest that MYC is involved: 1) we focused on
592 validated MYC binding sites (based on available MYC CHIP-seq data); 2) luciferase reporter assay for
593 selected E-boxes showed decreased transcription after MYC knockdown; 3) CHIP confirmed that E-
594 box disruption reduced MYC binding. Altogether, this indicates that, the activity of the studied E-
595 boxes is at least in part regulated by MYC, although we cannot exclude involvement of other factors.

596 **CONCLUSIONS**

597 In summary, the combined high-throughput screens using the MYC-EBOX-CRISPR library targeting E-
598 boxes and the Brunello library for gene knockout is a useful tool for genome-wide identification of E-
599 boxes which are important for MYC-dependent networks in cancer cells. This well-validated novel
600 approach allows for the identification of essential MYC-bound E-boxes and the regulated target
601 genes in MYC-dependent cancers. The broad design enables studies in a variety of cancer cell types
602 and determination of common as well as cell-type specific targets. Further testing in normal cells
603 may facilitate identification of potential novel therapeutic targets.

604

605 **AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS**

606 AD-K planned and supervised the project and acquired funding; MK, MŻ, MP, MEK, WS, WŁ, IZ-S and
607 AD-K performed the experiments; TW designed the MYC-EBOX-CRISPR library sgRNAs; data were
608 analyzed by MK, MP, WŁ, NR and AD-K; NR, JK and AvdB contributed to project conceptualization;
609 MK and AD-K prepared the figures and wrote the manuscript. All authors read and approved the
610 manuscript.

611

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617 Netherlands, and Dr. Maciej Giefing from the Institute of Human Genetics, Poland, for inspiring
618 discussions.

619 Figures: 2A and 2B were created using BioRender.

620 The results shown in Supplementary Table S11 are in part based upon data generated by the TCGA
621 Research Network: <https://www.cancer.gov/tcga>.

622 **COMPETING INTERESTS**

623 The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

624 **DATA AVAILABILITY**

625 Script used to generate MYC-EBOX-CRISPR library is deposited on github:

626 https://github.com/tomaszwozniakihg/cas9_search_tool

627 MYC-EBOX-CRISPR library was deposited in Addgene (#173195).

628

629 **Table 1. Performance of the screen in MYC-dependent cancer cell lines conducted in duplicate.**

	K562		ST486		HepG2		MCF7	
	Transduction efficiency	Coverage						
MYC-EBOX-CRISPR #1	32%	540x	26.2%	435x	29%	485x	30%	500x
MYC-EBOX-CRISPR #2	26.9%	455x	32.1%	535x	33.3%	560x	25.4%	425x
Brunello #1	23%	390x	37.5%	625x	26.2%	440x	24.1%	405x
Brunello #2	24.5%	415x	34.6%	575x	24.1%	405x	23.7%	400x

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644 **FIGURES**

645

646 **Figure 1. Design and generation of the MYC-EBOX-CRISPR library for genome-wide disruption of MYC binding**

647 **sites. A)** Library was designed based on publicly available MYC-ChIP-seq data in MYC-dependent K562, MCF7,

648 HepG2 and Burkitt lymphoma (BL) cell lines. After excluding E-boxes in coding exons, all possible sgRNAs

649 targeting remaining E-boxes were designed, based on the presence of PAM sequence. sgRNAs with predicted

650 off-target binding were filtered out. Final library contains 43,350 sgRNAs targeting E-boxes, 1,000 non-targeting

651 (NT) sgRNAs as a negative control, and four sgRNAs targeting MYC as a positive control. **B)** Number of sgRNA

652 constructs per E-box. **C)** Genomic location of E-boxes targeted by the library. **D)** Overlap of targeted E-boxes for

653 selected cancer cell lines. **E)** Percentage of MYC binding sites targeted by the MYC-EBOX-CRISPR library in

654 various cell lines, based on available MYC-ChIP-Seq data. In red are cell lines for which the library was designed.

655 **F)** Distribution of sgRNA constructs in the MYC-EBOX-CRISPR plasmid library determined by NGS. All sgRNAs

656 were present in the library.

657

658 **Figure 2. High-throughput screen with MYC-EBOX-CRISPR and Brunello libraries. A)** Experimental approach: 1)

659 MYC-EBOX-CRISPR library to destroy E-box sequences, disrupt MYC binding and its effect on target gene

660 expression 2) Brunello library for genome-wide gene knock-out. **B)** Scheme of the high-throughput screen in

661 cancer cells with MYC-EBOX-CRISPR and Brunello libraries. **C)** DESeq2 analysis revealed essential genes in

662 Brunello library and **D)** essential E-boxes in MYC-EBOX-CRISPR (depleted genes and E-boxes in blue, enriched

663 genes in red). **E)** Circos plots showing log₂ fold change (FC) values for genes in Brunello screen (outer circle)

664 and E-boxes in MYC-EBOX-CRISPR screen (inner circle) across the chromosomes. Blue dots indicate genes and

665 E-boxes significantly ($p_{adj} < 0.001$) depleted or enriched, black lines denote $\log_2FC=0$. **A)** and **B)** were created

666 using BioRender.

667

668

669

670 **Figure 3. Essential MYC-regulated processes and pathways.** A) Top 5 Gene Ontology (GO) terms for essential
 671 genes from Brunello library. B) Top 5 GO terms for genes localized up to 50 kb from essential E-boxes. C)
 672 Overlap of essential E-boxes from MYC-EBOX-CRISPR library. D) Overlap of essential genes from Brunello
 673 library.

674

675 **Figure 4. Validation of selected E-boxes and target genes.** **A)** Efficiency of disruption of selected E-boxes and
 676 the spectrum of mutations introduced by individual sgRNAs, demonstrated by TIDE analysis. Size distribution of
 677 introduced indels ranged from ≤ -30 bp to +2 bp. Colors indicate percentage of sequences with a given indel
 678 size. **B)** qRT-PCR analysis of genes adjacent to selected E-boxes upon CRISPR/Cas9 disruption of E-box
 679 sequences. Known MYC-regulated genes are underlined; genes essential or at least 4-fold depleted in Brunello

680 screen are in red. Noncoding genes are in green. Despite the name “antisense”, PRKCQ-AS1 does not overlap
681 with PRKCQ. NT – average of two non-targeting (negative control) sgRNAs. Mean and SD of two independent
682 experiments, each performed in triplicate, are shown. **, $p < 0.01$; ***, $p < 0.001$, Student’s t-test. **C)** Cell viability
683 upon disruption of selected E-boxes and knockout of adjacent genes was measured using CellTiter-Glo assay at
684 three timepoints: 0, 48 and 96 hours. Shown are mean values and SD from three independent experiments,
685 each performed in triplicate. *, $p < 0.05$; **, $p < 0.01$; ***, $p < 0.001$; ****, $p < 0.0001$, Student’s t-test. **D)**
686 Luciferase reporter assay for selected E-boxes upon MYC knockdown with shRNA. Decreased luminescence
687 signal was observed for all E-boxes in MYC-shRNA samples vs. NT control. **, $p < 0.01$; ****, $p < 0.0001$,
688 Student’s t-test. Mean and SD of three independent experiments, each performed in triplicate, are shown.
689 MYC-RE – MYC responsive element, positive control; EV – empty vector, negative control. **E)** MYC ChIP-qPCR
690 analysis of MYC binding upon E-box disruption. Cells were infected with sgRNAs targeting selected E-boxes.
691 MYC binding was decreased for chr17_BS377 and for chr10_BS212 but not for chr11_BS79. Mean and SD from
692 three replicates is shown.

693

694 **Figure 5. E-box disruption inhibits tumor growth in vivo.** HepG2 cells transduced with a non-targeting (NT)
 695 control sgRNA or sgRNAs targeting E-boxes on chr1, chr11 and chr18 were subcutaneously injected into
 696 NOD/SCID mice (NT n=6 tumors; chr1 n=8; chr11 n=4; chr18 n=8). **A)** Confirmation of the decreased growth of
 697 HepG2 cells *in vitro* upon targeting selected E-boxes. Shown are mean values and SD from three independent
 698 experiments, each performed in triplicate. *, p<0.05; **, p<0.01; ***, p<0.001; ****, p<0.0001, Student's t-
 699 test. **B)** Luciferase-based bioluminescence imaging of tumors over 5 weeks, mean and SEM. *, p<0.05; ***,

700 p<0.001, 2-way Anova. **C**) Representative images of luciferase-based bioluminescence imaging at week 5. **D**)
 701 Volume of tumors excised from mice, median with interquartile range. *, p<0.05, Kruskal-Wallis test with
 702 Dunn's post test. **E**) Representative images of excised tumors [cm].

703

704 **Figure 6. Grammar of the E-box sequence context. A)** Expression of two genes adjacent to an E-box on
 705 chromosome 10 (chr10_BS212) was examined in monoclonal cell lines derived from K562 cells transduced with
 706 an sgRNA targeting this E-box. A spectrum of clones with various modifications of the E-box were obtained,
 707 including: wild type (WT) homozygotes (n=7; K562 cells are triploid); homozygotes with the +G insertion after
 708 E-box (n=3); clones with two WT alleles and one mutated allele (n=2); clones with one WT allele and two
 709 mutated alleles (n=3); clones with various indels on all three alleles (n=9). Median with interquartile range is
 710 shown; *, p<0.05, Kruskal-Wallis test with Dunn's post test. **B)** Sequence logo (created using Seq2Logo) of the
 711 E-boxes and 20 nt flanking sequences for non-essential E-boxes (left, n=24,705) and E-boxes essential in at least
 712 one cell line (right, n=276). **C)** Frequency of up to 10 nt upstream/downstream flanking essential (n=276) and
 713 non-essential (n=24,705) E-boxes. Since E-boxes are (quasi)palindromic and can be read on either strand, G at
 714 +1 equals C at -1 etc. *, p<0.05; **, p<0.01; ***, p<0.001; ****, p<0.0001; chi-square goodness of fit test.

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